

Variant of Laparoscopic Lateral Suspension of the Uterus by Autologous Tissue (Round Ligament): A case study

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Abstract

The article discusses a clinical case of lateral isthmofixation with autologous tissue (round ligament), which can be used in patients with diagnosed prolapse.

More Information

How to cite this article: Sait, Zemouchi, Blidia, Henni, Farah. Variant of Laparoscopic Lateral Suspension of the Uterus by Autologous Tissue (Round Ligament): A case study. Eur J Med Health Res, 2024;2(6):69-71.
DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2024.2(6).08

Keywords:
prolapse, latero isthmofixation, round ligament.

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Introduction

Conservative treatment in prolapse is an increasingly considered therapeutic option, especially when the patient is young and intends to have children. The known therapeutic options are: prom onto fixation and the latero isthmofixation by the strips (technique of Kapandji) and at the level of the iliac crests front superior [1, 2].

Here we describe a variant of the latero isthmofixation by autologous tissue (round ligament) which is in my opinion an easier technique to perform with a shortened operating time and avoiding the harmful reactions of the strips, this technique can also bring an improvement in significant retroversion of the uterus.

Methodology

Patient and Methods

Patient aged 64,gsBrh+, G11P8C2,menopausalfor 19 years, who has had pelvic organ drop for 2 years with urination problems with:

- Valve examination anterior: Rectocele 2nd degree "R2»
- Valve examination posterior: Colcystocele 2nddegree "C2" ,hysteroptosis2nd degree "H2"

Surgical technique:

- Under AG
- Iterative LMSO type incision
- Nodetachment uterovesico vaginal

- Incision at the level of the spiked front superior right and left 10 mm opposite the round ligament

- Tullization untilround ligament by peritone umparietal.

We proceed to the latero-suspension of the uterus by autologous tissue by raising the round ligament at its origin. The latter is introduced into the two tunnel speritoneals already created and lastly we fix the round ligament under the skin deeply.

The fixation is made by a non-absorbable thread L'uterusis not pulled but suspended.

Closing plan by plan.

We complete the procedure with a second step via the lower route:

- Cure of cystoceleby a bursa and plication of the fascia of halban;
- Closure of the posterior angle by asacrosprofixation "intervention of Richter".

Description of techniques

Technique of promon to fixation: consists of compensating for tissue weakness by interposing 2 prostheses in front and behind the vagina, and compensating for the lack of suspension of the organs by fixing the prosthesis located between the vagina and the bladder, to the promontory (ligament in front of the disc located between the last lumbar vertebra L5 and the first sacral vertebra S1).

Technique of Kapandji technique described in 1967 used a non-absorbable strip of tissue which started the uterine isthmus at the iliac spine anterosuperior. A surgical procedure that corrects genital prolapse by reintegrating the organs into the pelvic cavity to restore normal anatomy. They remain held in good position using synthetic bandages. She consists of intervening most often by incision type pfannestiel (but can be

done by waycoelioscopic) followed by uterine abruption vesicovaginal. After this, lateral hysteropexy is performed by installing a stretched strip between the two iliac spines anterosuperior, previously fixed to the anterior face of the isthmus. The intervention is completed with aextraperitonization of the strip by making subperitoneal tunnels and lateral mooring of the strip.

Figure1: Exposition of the Hysteropexis h2

Figure2: Suspension of the Uterus by Round Ligament

Figure 3 :Post operative Control Day 20

Figure 4: Control 5 Months Post Operative

Discussion

The objective of this technique is: its speed, simplicity and shortening of the operating time. It seems to be

effective if necessary, no recurrences after 6 months, it also corrects uterine retroversions which are sometimes the source of pain and infertility.

The relatero-suspension of the uterus by autologous tissue using the round ligament reduces the risk of complications occurring when using slings such as sling infections, hematomas, the risk of occlusion if the intestine is in contact with the sling, erosion or rejection. It can be offered to young women with ahysteroptosis isolated 2nd degree and elderly women by classic route and orcoelioscopic avoiding any synthetic material.

Conclusion

The management of genital prolapse remains essentially surgical, however this correction requires a careful semiological analysis of the defects of the different levels of the pelvic floor.

The correct suspension of the vaginal fundus, bladder and rectum with reinforcement of the pelvic floor is the objective of the various surgical techniques used to

treat genital prolapse through the different approaches. The major element to be taken into account in the evaluation of surgical techniques remains essentially the long-term evolution.

References

- [1] Wagner L, Macia F, Delmas V, Haab F, Costa P. Traitement chirurgical du prolapsus par promontofixation par laparotomie: principes techniques et résultats [Surgical treatment of prolapse using laparoscopic promontofixation: technical principles and results]. Prog Urol. 2009 Dec;19(13):988-93. French. doi: 10.1016/j.purol.2009.09.024
- [2] Bendimrad H, et al. Surgical management of genital prolapse: Experience of the obstetrics and gynecology department of the Mohammed VI University Hospital in Marrakech. Faculty of Medicine and Pharmacy of Casablanca; 2017.

